

Exocrine Pancreatic Insufficiency in Dogs and Cats

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Abstract

The aim of the manuscript is detailed about the exocrine pancreatic insufficiency, its etiology, susceptible breeds, pathophysiology, clinical signs, diagnosis, treatment and prognosis of the disease in dogs and cats.

Introduction

Pancreas is a V- shaped gland lying close to the greater curvature of stomach and duodenum. The pancreas has two separate and distinct functions are endocrine and exocrine functions (Fig 1). The exocrine secretions from the pancreas are carried to the small intestine by the pancreatic duct. The pancreatic juice contains enzymes, bicarbonates, trophic factors and intrinsic factor. The enzymes produced by the gland are essential for digestion of carbohydrate, fat and proteins. The bicarbonates will help to maintain pH in the intestine which facilitates the active and passive transport of nutrients. Trophic factors and intrinsic factor help in absorption of certain essential elements and vitamins. Lack of secretion of pancreas enzyme led to maldigestion and malabsorption results in exocrine pancreatic insufficiency in dogs and cats (Williams 1996).

Fig 1: Anatomy position and microscopic view of pancreas

Exocrine pancreatic insufficiency (EPI)

Exocrine pancreatic insufficiency (EPI) is a syndrome caused by insufficient synthesis and secretion of digestive enzymes by the exocrine portion of the pancreas (Fig 2). The causes are congenital (present from birth), inherited (genetic), pancreatic acinar atrophy (dogs), auto-immune mediated and acquired causes are pancreatic infection, inflammation, or injury (Chronic pancreatitis (cats), Pancreatic neoplasia/ hypoplasia and Pancreatic flukes) (Williams and Batt, 1988).

Susceptible breeds are Chow Chows, Cavalier King Charles Spaniels, Rough-Coated Collies German Shepherd and Eurasian dog.

Pathophysiology

Lack of digestive enzymes may lead to maldigestion, osmotic diarrhea, and bacterial overgrowth in the small intestine. Bicarbonate: lack of bicarbonate affects intra-luminal pH of the intestine which affects to efficacy of brush border enzymes and can contribute to bacterial overgrowth. Trophic factors for GI mucosa: lack of trophic factors contributes to malabsorption. Intensive factor: lack of intrinsic factor leads to hypcobalaminemia as intrinsic factor is required for cobalamin transport in the ileum (Williams and Batt, 1988).

Fig 2: Structure of normal pancreas and pancreas with exocrine pancreatic insufficiency in dogs

Clinical signs

Common clinical signs of EPI are chronic diarrhea or very soft, bulky and fatty looking feces (steatorrhea), excessive appetites (polyphagia), vomiting, dry hair coat, coprophagia, flatulence, polydipsia and gradual weight loss over a period of months. Young adult dogs are often affected with EPI (Williams and Batt, 1988, Steiner and Williams 1999).

Diagnosis

Based on the history and clinical signs exhibited by the animals. The gold-standard test is Canine trypsinogen-like immunoassay (cTLI) for dogs, animals should be fasted for least 12-14 hours prior to blood draw. The dogs with EPI have cTLI of $< 2.5 \mu\text{g/L}$ (Normal value is $5.7\text{-}45.2 \mu\text{g/L}$) and animals in the border line will have the value of $2.5 - 5 \mu\text{g/L}$ (William and Batt 1988). The cats with EPI have cTLI of $< 8.0 \mu\text{g/L}$ (Normal value is $8\text{-}12 \mu\text{g/L}$) and animals in the border line will have the value of $12\text{-}82 \mu\text{g/L}$ (Steiner and Williams, 2000). Decline cTLI in combination with Vitamin B12 and folate level. Feecal microscopy can be a useful adjunctive diagnostic method. Stains such as Sudan or Iodine can stain the undigested fat and starch present in the feces respectively. Measures the fecal pancreatic elastase concentration (cE1) is valid in dogs. The cE1 concentration is $> 20 \mu\text{g/g}$ exclude EPI and $< 10 \mu\text{g/g}$ may have EPI. Assessment of serum amylase and lipase activities is not useful in diagnosis.

Treatment

Treatment is usually for the rest of the dog's life. Management with diet and medications. High quality, easily digestible, low-fat diets (not free of fat) together with pancreatic enzyme replacement will usually stabilize the condition (Steiner and Williams (2000) and Williams (1996).

- 1. Pancreatic enzyme replacement** (Tradename-Pancreasole[®], Viokase[®], Pancreazyme[®], Pank-Aid[®] and Zymogen[®])

- Powder form is more effective than tablets, capsules (enteric-coated products).
 - 1 teaspoon of drug/10 kg should be given with each meal for dogs.
 - 1 teaspoon of drug/cat with each meal for cats.
 - Once the clinical signs have completely resolved, the dose can be slowly decreased until the lowest effective dose has been reached.
 - Adverse effect is oral bleeding can be reified by moistening the food and pancreatic powder mix.
 - Fresh pancreas of beef, pork and sheep weighing (store up to 3 months) 1–3 oz (30–90 g) can replace 1 teaspoon of pancreatic powder
2. **Cobalamin (vitamin B12) supplementation** -Hypocobalaminemia occurs due to lack of intrinsic factor for absorption and increased uptake by intestinal bacteria. Serum cobalamine is in the low normal range < 300 ng/L. Cobalamin dose in dogs 250-1500 µg SQ weekly for 6 weeks and cats with 250 µg SQ weekly. After the 6 loading doses, subsequent doses are given every month.
 3. **Antibiotics** -Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth is a common problem in EPI. The undigested food in the intestine is a good substrate for bacterial growth. In addition, Changes in intestinal motility and immune function in EPI patients may allow bacteria to overgrow. Antibiotics are recommended to diarrhea cases; it does not resolve with initial treatment or signs recur on long term management. Tylosin (10-20 mg/kg PO q12hr) or Metronidazole (7.5-10 mg/kg PO q12hr) are more effective.
 4. **Antacids**- A large portion of orally administered lipase is destroyed by the low pH in the stomach. Antacids are recommended for diarrhea, if it does not resolve after other modifications have been attempted. Proton pump inhibitors were superior to histamine-2 blockers for EPI patients. Drugs like Famotidine (0.5-1 mg/kg PO q 12hr) or Omeprazole (0.7 mg/kg PO q24hr) are commonly used.

Prognosis

In EPI, irreversible loss of pancreatic acinar tissue is recorded. By the time clinical signs of EPI appear, pancreatic destruction is almost total, therefore lifelong enzyme therapy is usually required. Response to treatment (weight gain, cessation of diarrhea and decrease in fecal volume) is typically seen within the first few weeks of treatment. Dogs with marked hypocobalaminemia had worse survival rate (Williams and Batt, 1988).

Conclusions

Exocrine pancreatic insufficiency (EPI) is a syndrome due to insufficient synthesis of enzymes / irreversible changes in the pancreatic gland results in maldigestion and malabsorption in dogs and cats. Animals should undergo lifelong pancreatic enzyme replacer therapy and supplemented with cobalamine.

References

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